

The Use of Games as A Support Tool for Active Learning in The Context Of 4.0 Industry

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Abstract

Active methodologies have been gaining space among learning approaches since the results positively evaluated in terms of skills development, whether technical or transversal, and the assimilation of knowledge from different areas. There are several approaches used in face-to-face and distance higher education, such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Game-based Learning (GBL), Gamification, Serious Games, among others that place the student at the centre of their learning process. The advent of Industry 4.0 brought challenges to the teaching-learning of future engineers who will work in this new era. Therefore, the use of games or just elements of them is an ally in this challenge of transferring knowledge and maintaining the engagement and motivation of this generation of students in which games are inserted in their daily lives, being in common use for most of them. This work aims to present a study on the adequacy of games as a driving tool highlighting the applications, advantages, and difficulties of its use. An extensive literature review was the basis for the research and as result game application models in Industry 4.0 context and technological changes are presented.

Keywords: Active Learning, Game-Based Learning, Gamification, Engineering, Education challenges, Professional skills.

1 Introduction

The labor market is undergoing several changes in the evolution of industry 4.0 (Blackwell et al., 2013). The use of mobile and digital technologies is expanding in various sectors of society. However, in the context of learning, that does not occur in the same way.

Despite the universities' abilities to offer high-quality education, many employers still consider recent graduates unprepared for the job market, especially in professional skills such as communication, creativity, and collaboration (Eichelman, Clark & Bodnar, 2015).

To satisfy this demand, universities need to develop better ways to instruct students to prepare and help them to retain acquired knowledge and develop soft skills. According to Cheville (2012), many engineering students start their degrees without a high level of motivation and engagement. But, even the motivated, if the learning approaches adopted are not appropriate, this motivation may decrease. According to Souza et al. (2016), it is of paramount importance for universities the capability to captivate students so they can successfully acquire the desired skills, with the support of innovative methods of knowledge dissemination.

However, the traditional teaching approaches have not been demonstrated the most appropriate way to engage students and are, therefore, prone to lower levels of teaching and knowledge retention (Souza et al., 2016). Thus, to improve student performance and prepare them the best for the job market, active teaching-learning methodologies can be used in this process. However, some authors argue that even the PBL methodology, used in its traditional form, may prove to be insufficient to meet the demand of industry 4.0. Therefore, the use of games can come as a support to the teaching of concepts and abstracts and a way to motivate students to be consistent in their studies (Daba, Rosmansyah & Dabarsyah, 2019).

Therefore, this work aims to present a study on the use of games in the context of teaching engineering, highlighting the applications, advantages, and difficulties of its use. In general, the article seeks to answer and analyse how games can be applied as a teaching tool in the context of Industry 4.0. The authors carried out an extensive literature review to achieve this goal, and, as a result, presented a model of application of games in the context of the skills demanded by Industry 4.0.

2 Methodology

To achieve the research objective, a literature review was conducted using a method presented by Reis et al. (2020), which is an adaptation of the methods of Vieira & Gomes (2009), Borrego et al. (2014), Reis et al. (2017) and Mariano & Rocha (2017). This adapted method was chosen to conduct the research because, according to Reis (2020), they illustrate literature review procedures related to interdisciplinary fields, such as the investigation carried out by this present research, which goes through several areas related to Games and Active Learning in the context of Industry 4.0. This adapted method is divided into three stages, as presented by Reis et al (2020): definition of the research object; selection of the relevant articles to the purpose of the study; and deepening and developing the study.

In the first stage, based on Mariano & Rocha (2017), Borrego et al. (2014) and Vieira & Gomes (2009), it is necessary to define the scientific research databases and the research strings/terms. Therefore, the scientific databases chosen were Web of Science (WoS), Scopus and IEEE Xplore, as they are among the most important scientific databases, and their exclusion could negatively impact research. (Vieira & Gomes, 2009; Reis et al., 2017; Mariano & Rocha, 2017). The terms "game" AND ("problem-based learning" OR "project-based learning" OR "active learning" OR "active methodolog*") AND "engineering" were the strings used, filtering by the last five years. Thus, the research returned a total of 404 articles on the subject, being 182 from Scopus, 114 studies from WoS and 108 from IEEE Xplore.

The second stage is the step in which the relevant articles for the purpose of the study are selected. For that it is necessary to fix duplicate results, in other words, articles found in more than two databases (Reis et al., 2020). This duplication can be seen mainly between the Scopus and WoS bases. Then, the most relevant papers were separated according to the theme to be analysed separately.

The third stage is characterized by deepening and developing the study. Thus, according to the adapted methodology of Reis et al (2020), the 52 articles resulting from the second step were analysed in detail to allow a better understanding of the subject and to detach relevant elements for teaching engineering based on the use of games for learning, namely: how the use of games is being applied for active learning; focusing on the benefits and difficulties of this application; how game-based teaching is impacting the learning of future engineers; and how the advancement of industry 4.0 is impacting the formation of this new era of education.

3 The use of games as a tool to support active learning in the context of industry 4.0

3.1 Industry 4.0 challenges

The challenges of the job market are gradually more elaborated, in order to respond to the different needs that arise and walk along with the innovations. According to Sancho, Torrente, Marchiori and Fernández-Manjón (2011), the companies that follow the market have started to focus on their way of working in integrated activities instead of activities where professionals work alone.

The skills required for this generation are more complex and more essential skills are expected for the role of an engineer (Bermúdez, Rodríguez, Nistal, de Carvalho & Nogueira, 2015). Considering the current scenario, based on Andrade, Gouveia, Nogueira, Russo, and de Carvalho (2015), employers are looking for newly graduated engineers who have the skills to learn throughout life, key competencies that can influence the work environment, resourcefulness to solve real problems and advanced proximity to the digital environment.

The features skills presented by Sancho et al. (2011), De Graaf, E., & Kolmos, A. (2003), Karre, H., Hammer, M., Kleindienst, M. & Ramsauer, C. (2017), Kolmos et al. (2007) and Kolmos, A., Dahms, M.-L., & Du, X. (2010), could be grouped in five main skills that represent the majority ideas of the cited abilities. These main skills are presented and defined underneath:

- **Problem-solving skills** - an ability to identify, analyse, and solve applied science problems, through analytical skills and critical thinking based on knowledge of contemporary issues.

- **Management skills** - involves the ability to deal with constant changes, self and time management, organizational and processual understanding, and failure analysis.
- **Communication skills** - an ability to communicate clearly and effectively orally and written form, as also disseminating the knowledge in an intercultural team.
- **Professional skills** - an ability to use the techniques, skills, and modern scientific and technical tools necessary for professional practice, also the ability to interact with modern interfaces and have the resilience to adapt to new and different situations. These abilities would be combined with interdisciplinary competencies and an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility.
- **Social skills** - development of social abilities as leadership, responsibility, reliability and ability to work in multidisciplinary teams.

3.2 Game-based teaching-learning methodologies

The professional identity of students begins to be developed in the university environment; therefore, this environment must bring real experiences of the needs of the industry (Zajc & Starcic, 2017).

Project-Based Learning (PBL), is a teaching approach in which each student plays the fundamental role for their learning by being actively involved in the process (Cain & Cocco, 2013). In this process students develop some important skills for the future profession such as: communication, leadership, effectiveness, professionalism, management skills (Monteiro, Lima, Junior & Mariano, 2019).

In the literature review by Junior et al (2019), the authors found two predominant strands of methodologies in the application of games in education. The first was Game-Based Learning (GBL) which uses games as a way to improve the learning process, and the second was Gamification which uses game elements to motivate learning.

The GBL, in order to keep students motivated in learning, makes activities more engaging, in addition, due to this attractive and interactive method, some students tend to learn better in these scenarios (All, Castellar & Van Looy, 2015). According to All, Castellar, and Van Looy (2015), the use of the GBL methodology helps to create additional motivation which, in turn, can help to improve the effectiveness of teaching skills to students.

According to Abdool, Ringis, Maharajh, Sirju and Abdool (2017), Gamification is the process of applying elements of social games (such as role-playing, scoring systems) to real-world situations, which has long been time used in the educational system to promote the involvement of participants, seeking a balance between rigor and clemency.

However, in some cases, the motivation and involvement of participants decreases over time, if the mechanics of gamification are applied incorrectly (Hanus & Fox, 2015). For this reason Deterding (2012) suggests that, in addition to the elements of the game, the game design should also be used to successfully capture the interest of the participant, so that they should be incorporated into the course curriculum in some attractive and meaningful way to maintain the student's interest.

When used well, both the use of games and gamification can be excellent teaching tools, preparing engineers so that they feel more motivated and involved in the learning process. Also, according to Souza et al. (2016), using Games can make students not feel bored and/or anxiety states, maintaining the learning flow.

Besides, Pantelidis (1996) argues that virtual reality can also be used in teaching and, more specifically, in engineering teaching. Virtual reality allows students to enjoy real problem simulations, in addition, to be an immersive and highly engaging system. Nelson and Ahn (2018), address the use of virtual reality as a tool for teaching engineering students, with a focus on professional development skills. Nelson and Ahn (2018) also comment on the study by Abulrub, Attridge, and Williams (2011), which discusses how virtual reality can lead students to more creative solutions to the problem they are trying to solve, as it allows students to explore different solutions in a reasonably secure space that they couldn't do in the real world.

3.3 The use of games in the context of industry 4.0

Case studies regarding the application of games have been growing in engineering, the result of interest on the subject. These works mainly demonstrate the benefits of their application in the classroom or in the course.

With the growing importance of teaching the fundamentals of database and the need to incorporate ideas of design, administration and maintenance, as well as data analysis and knowledge discovery, an elective course on postgraduate database systems at the University of the West Indies sought in games the solution for under-enrolment of students in the course (Abdool et al., 2017). To solve these questions, a game based on RPG and references from pop culture was developed in the delivery and evaluation of the course to increase students' interest and motivation. According to Abdool et al. (2017), RPG cards were used, using pop culture references to specific animation series and fantasy game genres, with game elements such as experience points (XP) and teammates. According to student feedback, there was a significant increase in interest in the course, in addition to indicating a strong positive feeling about the DATARPG system, the name given to the game, which also contributed to the retention and mastery of the content (Abdool, Ringis, Maharajh, Sirju & Abdool, 2017).

In Brazil, there was also an attempt to encourage students to develop their programming skills at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte. In 2013, the university underwent a structural change in the Information Technology (IT) courses that increased the number of vacancies in the university admission process. Considering the rising failure rate in introductory subjects, teachers began to adopt a new approach to teaching methodology for first-year students. This approach needed to encourage students to practice programming, considering a game-based approach as the preferred method for engagement strategies in addition to: providing problem-based learning; be accessible from any computer; be adaptable to the course schedule defined by the teachers; and, be useful throughout the academic period. After some research and historical studies of methodologies previously used at the University, they decided to develop an internal solution (Kodesh) that introduced game mechanics to the programming learning process. During the process they also performed group dynamics based on games. In the Kodesh environment and dynamics, they used elements of games such as teammates, points, virtual coins, leaderboards, clues and instant feedback. This work was done in an introductory programming course and there was a significant improvement in student performance (Campos, Batista, Signoretti, Gardiman and Madeira, 2015).

Another format for the use of games was presented in the case study of the article "Proposal of Global PBL Education for Engineers using Sequence Learning Kit" by Yajima et al. (2018) held at KIMTL college -Thailand, in partnership with Sendai college -Japan, in its engineering courses. The objective of the study was to investigate the result of the implementation of a basic kit of a sequence of controls, the central problem of a project stimulated by the techniques of games and spirit of competition, for the development of knowledge and generic skills. To carry out the experiment, an e-Learning system was used to transmit theoretical knowledge and a basic kit for assembling an electrical circuit as a pinball game. First with the delivery of the material and prior explanation; Then with the application of a class to align the student's level of knowledge and the lack of preliminary learning to configure the task; and finally, with e-Learning available weeks before, for learning. After the end of the estimated time for carrying out the activity, the groups presented themselves as a competition, worth points for the conclusion, originality, and design. It was observed that the students were able to learn in a pleasant way, in cooperation with friends and with good efficiency through the learning kit and the method. This conclusion, in addition to being confirmed and exposed by the students, was also estimated from a report to identify the students' skills, being done before and after the experiment, it was possible to prove the growth of the students' skills.

The use of games in the educational context presented itself as a more interactive method, helping to create additional motivation that, in turn, helps to improve the effectiveness in teaching skills and professional development (Nelson & Ahn, 2018; All, Castellar & Looy (2015) From the literature review, it was possible to elaborate a table to identify the elements that presented results in the process of developing competencies related to those required by industry 4.0 (Table 1).

Table 1. Skills developed from the use of games in active methodology.

Methodologies	Paper	Elements or types of game used	Skills developed
Game-Based Learning and Problem-Based Learning	Ustyuzhanina, Plotnikova and Efremova (2017)	Individual activities; Group activities.	Self-improvement; Teamwork; Communication; Decision-making; Assimilation of content
	Topalli and Cagiltay (2018).	Real-life game development projects. Visual Programming and Projects.	Perform better in programming
	Maksimova, Kutrunova, Maksimov and Voronov (2017). Andrade, Gouveia, Nogueira, Russo and de Carvalho (2015)	Serious game (not virtual). Teammate. Reality simulation. Serious game (eCity); Virtual simulation.	Increase the communication and the motivation of students; Proactivity; Assimilation of content; Motivation; Solution of real problems with strategies.
	Abdool, Ringis, Maharajh, Sirju and Abdool (2017)	Role-Playing; Game (RPG).	Motivation; Time management; Assimilation of content
	Campos, Batista, Signoretti, Gardiman and Madeira (2015)	Learning platform (Rules, levels, quests, ranking, time-limit, point, virtual coins, buy helpful items).	Motivation; Teamwork; Communication; Self-improvement; Assimilation of content; Cooperation; Self-management; Computational thinking.
	Nelson and Ahn (2018)	Virtual Reality Game (avatars, virtual world, puzzle games, multiplayer).	Communication; Teamwork; Decision-making; Leadership; Collaboration; Solution of problem; Computational thinking
	Bermúdez, Rodríguez, Nistal, de Carvalho and Nogueira. (2015)	Serious game (eCity); Virtual simulation.	Leadership; Teamwork; Communication
E-learning	Datta and Bhattacharyya (2018)	Levels; Time-Limit; Puzzles.	Assimilation of contents
Gamificação and Problem-Based Learning	Sousa, Stadnicka, Dinis-Carvalho, Ratnayake and Isoherranen (2016)	Graphic Design; Simulation.	Motivation; Assimilation of contents
	Campos, Batista, Signoretti, Gardiman and Madeira (2015)	Learning platform (Rules, levels, quests, ranking, time-limit, point, virtual coins, buy helpful items).	Motivation; Teamwork; Communication; Self-improvement; Assimilation of content; Cooperation; Self-management; Computational thinking.
	Daba, Rosmansyah and Dabarsyah (2019)	Boards, video games, story-club, puzzle, canvas.	Performance; Engagement; Motivation; Assimilation of content
	Sagirani, Sunarto, Hariadi, Amelia and Lemantara (2018)	Story, challenge, curiosity, character, interactivity, feedback e freedom to fail.	Motivation; Engagement; Performance; Assimilation of concepts and content.
	Yajima, Maneerat, Sugaya, Nitta, Takeichi and Sato (2018)	Construction of a Pinball game; Competition.	Teamwork; Collaboration; Solution of problems; Motivation; Self-improvement; Logical reasoning; Assimilation of concepts and content; Communication.
	Yajima, Okumura, Sugaya, Takeichi and Sato (2015)	Competition; High score.	Teamwork; Motivation; Self-improvement; Logical reasoning; Assimilation of concepts and content; Communication.
	Abidin and Zaman, (2017). Rich et al (2018)	Points; Competition.	Engagement; Motivation; Concentration; Satisfaction; Assimilation of content

Considering the perspectives presented by Reis et al (2020) and the skills presented in Chart 1, it is clear that the use of games as an active methodology has been collaborating, mainly, in the perspective, training, and learning. The latter seeks to improve employees and students in complex concepts and subjects, in addition to encouraging the development of personal skills necessary in the industry, such as conflict resolution, communication, teamwork, and leadership.

Figure 1. Elements of games that bring skills required by Industry 4.0.

The Figure 1 presents the five more cited skills by industry 4.0 and some elements of games that, based on this literature review, help to develop the required skills since the university period of engineers. For instance, when the element of games chosen is a simulation or role-playing game or another kind of virtual simulation, skills as professional, problem-solving and management are developed and improved, whereas collaboration is an element of games most used to develop and improve communication and social skills.

4 Conclusions

The movement of industry 4.0 and technological advances, consequently, brought changes and new requirements for engineering professionals forcing the universities to adapt their teaching methodology and contents. One of the methodologies that are being used by universities is the use of games to teach and, in this paper, the use of this approach as an active learning support tool was evident.

The employers and companies are looking for minds that could handle the evolution of the market and, for that, more than theory is necessary, they are searching for people that have skills to adapt in different environments, establish new processes and products, effective communications, capability to grow and expand their business. The use of games in engineering courses proved to be very efficient in contributing to the development of abilities required by the job market, pointed by this literature review, as: management, communication, problem-solving, professional, and social skills. Furthermore, games act as a tool to keep students motivated for learning, increase satisfaction, and the ability to retain knowledge, as the games' interface allows for greater student interactivity with course content and contributes to professional training through innovation.

Thus, it was verified the importance of developing engineering knowledge and skills throughout the period of study at the university. The study brought the analysis of the game elements that are capable to improve the skills required, these elements can be seen in the case studies presented in this paper. In this new era based on advances in industry 4.0, the job market requires professionals to be capable of putting in practice their skills developed in the academy through their daily tasks and evolve transversal skills. The technologies associated with the use of games are an insertion factor for a generation focused on the frequent use of digital devices.

Game-based methodologies and gamification are capable of boosting learning but are still underutilized in universities. As challenging as its application may be, its introductions should be stimulated due to its benefits

and advantages for education. This paper brought the elements of games used in active methodologies that help the development of industry 4.0 required skills using the game as a support tool for active learning in the universities.

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